

A RAPID METHOD OF ESTIMATING SMALL AMOUNT OF IRON AND MANGANESE IN COPPER-NICKEL-ZINC ALLOYS.

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Estimation of small amount of iron (0.1 % max.) and manganese (0.3 % max.) in alloys containing copper (60-80 %), nickel (15-20 %), and zinc (20 %) meets with some difficulty. It is generally done in the laboratory by precipitating the hydroxides of iron and manganese by ammonia from a nitric acid solution of the alloys and precipitating it again so as to make it as much free from copper, nickel and zinc as possible. It is then ignited and weighed. The ignited oxides are dissolved in a few drops of hydrochloric acid and the latter is removed by nitric acid. Manganese is estimated by silver nitrate-persulphate method and the iron calculated by difference.

By this process the above precipitate cannot be made completely free from copper, nickel and zinc. Direct determination of iron by titanous sulphate, though rapid, suffers from the defect that the solution cannot be preserved unchanged for any length of time, as the strength of it is to be kept very weak (1 c.c. commercial $TiSO_4$ diluted upto 100 c.c. or even more).

The following method is suggested as an improvement. Iron is first determined by reducing the solution with metallic zinc and then titrating it with $N/50-KMnO_4$. Manganese is afterwards estimated by the ordinary arsenite method. As the amount of additional manganese, which has been introduced into the solution while titrating iron, is known, it is deducted from the final manganese content of the alloy.

Procedure.

The alloy (1 g.) is dissolved in 20 c.c. HNO_3 (d 1.2) and diluted to 100 c. c. with water. Bromine water (10-15 c.c.) is added and made ammoniacal. Mn and Fe are precipitated down as hydroxides; Cu, Ni and Zn remain in the solution. It is filtered and washed alternately 5 to 6 times with hot water and ammonia. A solution of sodium metabisulphite (5 %) containing H_2SO_4 (1:20) is freshly prepared and the precipitate is dissolved by adding this solution drop by drop. The solution is received in a conical flask, 5 to 6 c.c. concentrated H_2SO_4 are added together with 10 c.c. of 10% solution of ammonium persulphate. If any

sulphur separates out at this stage, it is oxidised by the persulphate on boiling. The solution is boiled for 5 minutes until the persulphate is completely decomposed. The solution is cooled to 60°, the iron is reduced in a Jone's apparatus and titrated against $N/50\text{-KMnO}_4$.

1 C.c. of $N/50\text{-KMnO}_4$ contains 0.00112% iron.

After the titration of iron the same solution is used for the determination of manganese.

A 0.5% solution (20 c.c.) of AgNO_3 (according to the percentage of manganese present) is introduced into the flask containing the solution for the estimation of iron and is heated to boiling. A 5% solution of ammonium persulphate (20 c.c.) is added to the boiling solution when the permanganate colour is developed. It is then cooled in running water. Finally $N/50$ -sodium arsenite solution is run in till the colour of the permanganate is discharged.

The sodium arsenite is standardised against a standard steel of known manganese content.

Sample No.	Iron present.	Iron found.	Total Mn. found.	Mn found after-deducting the Mn in $N/50\text{-KMnO}_4$.	Actual Mn. present.
1.	0.09%	0.09%	0.219%	0.20%	0.20%
2.	0.08	0.079	0.228	0.21	0.21
3.	0.10	0.098	0.209	0.19	0.195

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